

Innovative Business Models in Cultural Tourism: The Case of Cumalıkızık

Elif Yücel^{1*}, Nuran Bayram Arlı²

¹Bursal Uludag University, Faculty of Economics and Business Administrative Sciences, Department of Business Administration, Turkey

²Bursal Uludag University, Faculty of Economics and Business Administrative Sciences, Department of Econometrics, Turkey

Abstract

Cultural tourism is increasingly valued as both a means of preserving local cultures and a driver of economic development. Currently, cultural tourism, in its new forms with innovative business models, aims at the protection of cultural heritage in a sustainable way while bringing more economic benefits to the local communities. In this sense, such culturally rich settlements like the village of Cumalıkızık in Bursa are very good examples for the implementation of such innovative business models. This village earned its place as a UNESCO World Heritage Site with the preservation of samples of civil architectural works from the Ottoman era. These features allow this village to become an object for cultural tourism and open certain perspectives for the development of new business models. In addition, the innovative cultural tourism business models contrast with their approach: enriching experiences for visitors and supporting economic and sustainable tourism for local communities. This study analyses visitor experiences in Bursa's historic village of Cumalıkızık in detail. The analysis was conducted by examining visitor reviews shared on the Tripadvisor platform for the village and on Google for its restaurants. Based on the data obtained, innovative models were developed, and strategies and recommendations were proposed for advancing the cultural tourism of the village and differentiating its restaurants.

Keywords: Cultural Tourism, Business Innovation, World Heritage Site, Bursa

¹ Assoc Prof, Bursal Uludag University, Faculty of Economics and Business Administrative Sciences, Department of Business Administration, emugal@uludag.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2708-6778> (Corresponding author)

² Prof, Bursal Uludag University, Faculty of Economics and Business Administrative Sciences, Department of Econometrics, nuranb@uludag.edu.tr, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2708-6778>

1. Introduction

Cultural tourism encompasses the exploration of historical, artistic, scientific, and cultural elements. According to UNWTO (2018), it constitutes around 40% of global tourism activity (Richards, 2010). Beyond tangible heritage such as monuments and museums, cultural tourism also involves intangible aspects like traditions, oral histories, and crafts, as emphasized by UNESCO (Szromek, 2022). However, traditional cultural tourism models have been criticised for issues such as the overuse of tourist sites and the loss of authenticity, highlighting the need for their redesign (Richards & Wilson, 2007).

In recent years, creative and innovative business models have reshaped traditional cultural tourism. Innovation in tourism is not only about developing new products and services, but also about restructuring existing value creation processes (Bocken & Geradts, 2020). Innovative business models supported by digitalisation, social media and mobile applications enhance the visitor experience and improve the economic sustainability of local communities (Ammirato et al., 2022). The widely accepted "Gassmann's Magic Triangle" is a framework used to understand and analyse business model innovation in the tourism sector. This model clearly structures the fundamental components of business models around three main elements as seen in the Figure 1. (Gassmann et al., 2014):

- Who? – Who is the target customer group?
- What? – What is the value proposition offered to the customer?
- How? – How does the value creation process work?

These three key elements are interconnected and determine the success of the business model. The model helps to understand how business model innovations take shape and which components can be modified to gain a competitive advantage. At the centre of the “Magic Triangle” lies the revenue model, which explains how the above three elements are translated into financial gain. Businesses may utilize different revenue streams, such as subscription-based income, one-time sales, freemium models, or advertising revenues. This framework provides a strategic roadmap for understanding business model innovation and developing new business models. Gassmann and his team argue that most successful business model innovations occur through radical changes in at least one of these three components (Gassmann et al., 2014).

Figure 1: BMI Lab Methodology

In this respect, Cumalıkızık is a special cultural tourism destination with its Ottoman-period civil architecture, specific street makeup, and traditional life style. Inclusion in the UNESCO World Heritage List in 2014 contributed to an increased emphasis on the village's cultural and economic potential. However, innovation business models will be required in order to ensure a sustainable utilization of this potential. Different innovative approaches have been given a

face in cultural tourism, especially in achieving economic benefits to the local community, conservation of cultural heritage, and developing visitor experiences.

This research mainly aims to explore the effects of innovation in cultural tourism on local communities and the entire industry as a whole. The following study focuses on innovative business models within the context of cultural tourism in the case of Cumalıkızık Village in Bursa. First, customer comments on Tripadvisor and Google were examined related to the village and its restaurants. This analysis identified the current situation through the strengths and weaknesses of the village, along with the opportunities and threats arising, and also provided recommendations for the development of a model with the purpose of preserving the village's cultural heritage while enhancing its economic potential.

Unlike prior studies that examine cultural tourism at a macro level, this research introduces a micro-level, community-specific innovation framework, leveraging real-time user-generated content and participatory design with local stakeholders. The application of the Business Model Innovation (BMI) methodology to a small-scale heritage village represents a novel attempt to localize global sustainable tourism models.

2. Literature Review

The transformation of the global economy and advanced technologies have clearly identified key topics for the tourism sector. These include cultural heritage preservation, sustainable tourism policies and innovative business models. Cultural tourism is defined as the visitation of historical sites and the experience of local cultural elements by tourists (Bandoğlu, 2015). However, as in many other countries, cultural tourism in Turkey remains underutilised, with a lack of promotion being one of the primary obstacles to realizing its full potential (Meydan Uygur & Baykan, 2007). Studies on the case of Kars show that cross-border collaborations and well-planned tourism policies are vital for preserving cultural heritage and fostering sustainable development (Kocalar, 2024).

Innovation is a key driver in the development of cultural tourism. A comprehensive literature review by Işık et al. (2018) clearly shows that innovation research in the tourism industry focuses on business performance, managers' perceptions of innovation, and strategies for sustainable tourism. Uzun (2020) is spot on when he says that tourism companies need to invest in technological innovations to increase competitive advantage and develop customer experiences. Ammirato et al. (2022) also state that mobile application-based business models can improve the quality of the user experience in cultural tourism and must be tailored to meet the needs of each tourist. AR technology is set to transform the way people consume cultural heritage tourism services, though AR-based business models are still in their early stages (Cranmer & Jung, 2014).

Different studies conducted on the relationship between innovation and entrepreneurship in tourism present the ways in which smart destination applications have inspired transformation in the sector. Yavuz (2019) depicts that in smart destinations, there are major improvements in public administration, transportation, environmental sustainability, and tourist experiences. In addition, the aspect of digital business models transforming the tourism sector is evaluated based on the operation models of various platforms. For instance, Valsamidis et al. (2019) assert that digital intermediary business models such as those provided by Airbnb, TripAdvisor, Expedia, and Booking.com have already disrupted the tourism industry.

Against this background, creative cultural tourism recently emerged as another option to challenge the traditional conceptual thinking of tourism in response to new consumption styles. Al-Ababneh and Masadeh (2019) comment that creative tourism moves tourists from passive

consumers to experience-based participants. Also, Richards (2021) has analysed some creative tourism business models, discussing the growing development of interactive experience concepts enabled in tourism by digital platforms and social media.

The discussion of the role of business model innovation in the integration of tourism with the purposes of sustainable development is another popular direction of research today. Saebi et al. (2017) mention that business model innovation is vital for the possibility of achieving these goals of sustainable development, and especially circular and social business models that balance long-term economic success with ecological and social sides. In this regard, the study by Humlebæk and Pedersen (2023) finds that innovative contract models enhance collaboration among stakeholders in the preservation of cultural heritage.

The role of tourism in local development is another important area within the literature. The studies analysing the impact of rural tourism on regional development include its economic, social, and cultural dimensions. Research on the case of Cumalıkızık shows that rural tourism promotes local entrepreneurship, particularly creating opportunities for women entrepreneurs (Demir & Boz, 2017). However, while tourism activities contribute to increasing the region's recognition, it is emphasized that careful planning should be done so as not to harm environmental sustainability (Soylu et al. 2024).

In recent years, brands in the tourism and hospitality sector have utilized technology, social media, and constant connectivity to establish more organic interactions with consumers and to foster the co-creation of personalized customer services. The concept of real-time service enables dynamic and instant engagement with consumers. In this context, digital applications enriched with big data analytics, artificial intelligence, and contextual information have transformed the service creation process by enabling more efficient mobilization of resources within the tourism ecosystem. This approach, referred to as “nowness service,” reshapes tourism experiences based on five core elements: real-time interaction, co-creation, data-drivenness, consumer-centricity, and experience generation (Buhalis & Sinarta, 2019). Neuhofer et al. (2015), in their study, identified that smart system components—such as information aggregation, ubiquitous mobile connectivity, and real-time synchronization—form the foundational elements of experience personalization. The study emphasizes that smart technologies not only improve operational efficiency but also play a strategic role in the creation of meaningful and interactive experiences. In this regard, it is considered that digital integration can contribute significantly to cultural tourism, both in terms of user-centered service design and within the framework of the experience economy. Another study about digitalisation in tourism sector was written by Gretzel et al. (2015). They define smart tourism as a multidimensional system integrating smart destinations, digital business ecosystems, and technology-enhanced tourist experiences. By combining IoT, mobile connectivity, big data, and real-time interaction, smart tourism transcends traditional e-tourism, fostering value co-creation, open innovation, and business model transformation. Their framework underscores how digital ecosystems can reshape cultural tourism through personalized and context-aware experiences.

In general, the literature indicates that sustainability, innovation, and digitalization are the core of this new era that tourism is facing. It seems there is a move away from traditional cultural tourism toward creative tourism and experience-based tourism, for which digitalization acts as a very strong facilitator. Business model innovation can create substantial opportunities in terms of both sustainable development and competitive advantage, and even more innovative applications will be realized in the future of the tourism industry.

3. Methods

In this study, an eight-stage methodology for business model innovation was adopted and a systematic process was followed for the development of innovative business models related to Cumalıkızık village and its restaurants (as seen in Figure 2). A preliminary assessment phase was conducted to identify the current state of Cumalıkızık village and its restaurants. In this phase, the digital presence of the region was investigated by analysing websites and social media accounts and reviews provided by visitors. Additionally, the online reviews on various websites, such as TripAdvisor and Google, are included, supplemented by a SWOT analysis that puts into perspective strengths and weaknesses regarding this region. The qualitative data obtained from visitor reviews were analysed using MAXQDA, a qualitative data analysis software. A word frequency analysis was conducted to identify the most commonly mentioned themes in visitor experiences. This approach allowed for the detection of key topics that shape tourists' perceptions of Cumalıkızık, including both positive and negative aspects. The analysis process involved several steps:

- **Data Cleaning & Preprocessing:** The collected reviews were filtered to remove irrelevant content and duplicates.
- **Coding & Categorization:** Reviews were systematically coded into predefined categories based on thematic patterns.
- **Word Frequency Analysis:** The most frequently used words and phrases were identified, providing insights into recurring themes in visitor experiences.
- **Interpretation & Triangulation:** The results were cross-checked with findings from in-depth observations and stakeholder interviews to ensure reliability.

The findings from the word frequency analysis were used to develop innovative business model recommendations, addressing both the strengths and challenges identified in visitor feedback. Restaurants and places of tourist interest were visited in the region during the field experience where customer experiences could be directly observed. In-depth analysis was done on service quality, pricing policies, and customer expectations to understand the tourism and commercial structure of the region. Semi-structured interviews with local business owners, restaurant operators, tourists, and other related stakeholders were conducted to collect data on the business models that already exist and problems they face.

Using the collection of qualitative and quantitative data within the analytical framework of the BMI methodology, for the analysis, it used various tools: Business Model Canvas and Value Proposition Canvas. In fact, mapping was performed based on current business model dynamics in the region and places of innovative change; then techniques of brainstorming and innovation matrices were performed in order to outline innovative proposals for business models on sustainable tourism and local development. The proposed models have been shared with local business persons and stakeholders, and after receiving their feedback, the models are revised to enhance their feasibility. A phased implementation plan was thereafter developed to translate the selected proposals into practice; short and long-term strategies were identified. In the last stage of the research, the applicability of the developed model was checked, and recommendations for establishing a sustainable business ecosystem for Cumalıkızık village and its restaurants were presented concretely.

Figure 2: BMI Lab Methodology

This methodological process has enabled the development of a business model that enhances economic sustainability while preserving local values, strengthens the touristic appeal of the region, and integrates innovative approaches.

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, the current state of Cumalıkızık village was first analysed. For this purpose, visitor experiences towards the historical Cumalıkızık village of Bursa are examined in detail. The analysis was carried out through visitor comments shared on the Tripadvisor platform between 2018 and 2024. In the study, which was conducted with 2135 coding from the comments of 199 visitors in total, the categories of positive and negative experiences and the areas of improvement suggested by the visitors were comprehensively discussed. The distribution of visitor reviews by year and their classification by experience categories are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Visitor Experiences in Cumalıkızık Village by Year (2018–2024)

Code System	2024	2023	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018
Score							
1	7	3	4	2	2	9	
2	2	2			2	12	
3	3	3	2	3	6	20	3
4	2	2	3	2	5	18	5
5	4	4	3	4	10	49	3
City							
Outside the city	6	5	6	9	17	71	5
Within the city	2	1			3	9	4
Positive Experiences							
Hospitality and Local Culture			2	3	1	14	
Breakfast and Food Experience	1	2	2	1	2	14	4
Historical Texture and Natural Beauty	4	1	1	3	9	38	9

Negative Experiences							
Disappointment in Historical Texture	2		1	1	2	10	1
Breakfast and Food Experience	5	3	2	3	3	8	3
Crowds and Noise		1	1		3	6	6
Parking and Transportation Issues	2	1	1			8	1
Commercialization and Local Attitude	11	3	4	1	11	42	2
Suggestions and Neutral Observations							
General Information	2	1	1		1	9	1
Venue and Service Improvement		1	2			7	
Recommendations for Visiting Time		3	3	2	3	8	4

Table 1 presents a year-by-year categorization of visitor experiences in Cumalıkızık from 2018 to 2024. This breakdown enables us to observe not only the frequency of visits but also the nature of those experiences — positive, negative, or neutral. The most active year appears to be 2019, both in terms of satisfaction and dissatisfaction, which could relate to peak tourism and insufficient infrastructure preparedness. While high satisfaction was observed in categories such as "Hospitality and Local Culture" and "Breakfast and Food Experience," negative experiences related to "Disappointment with Historical Texture" and "Commercialization" were also prominently reported. By 2020, the number of both positive and negative experiences declined, likely due to the impact of the pandemic. The decrease in satisfaction with the "Historical Texture and Natural Beauty" category highlighted the need for improvements, while ongoing commercial and structural issues underscored the necessity of sustainable tourism policies. In 2023 and 2024, there was a general decline in visitor reviews. The prominence of rural tourism experiences indicated its potential, while the persistence of issues such as overcrowding, noise, and parking emphasized the need for infrastructure improvements. The high volume of negative reviews regarding 'Commercialization and Local Attitudes' (74 coded references) underscores a visitor perception of authenticity loss. In response, the proposed tourism policy emphasizes preserving Cumalıkızık's historical and natural assets, supported by zoning strategies and training programs for local merchants. Similarly, complaints about parking and overcrowding (13 mentions) inform infrastructure recommendations such as shuttle-based mobility systems and timed entry regulation. The decline in visitor interest post-pandemic has further emphasized the need for sustainable tourism strategies. The distribution of the ratings given by visitors to the Cumalıkızık village between 2018 and 2024 is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The Distribution of the Ratings Given by Visitors to the Cumalıkızık Village (2018 and 2024)

Figure 3 illustrates the overall satisfaction of visitors based on their ratings between 2018 and 2024. It shows the distribution of the total 199 ratings given to Cumalıkızık village. The highest proportion of ratings falls under the "5" category with 77 points, indicating a generally high level of visitor satisfaction. Following this, the "4" category stands out with 37 points, and

the "3" category with 40 points. However, the notable presence of lower ratings in the "1" (27 points) and "2" (18 points) categories suggests that some visitors' expectations were not met. This distribution indicates that while the village is generally positively evaluated, there is a need for improvement in certain areas.

The distribution of positive experiences of visitors to Cumalıkızık village between 2018 and 2024, categorized, is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of Positive Experiences of Visitors to Cumalıkızık Village by Categories (2018 and 2024)

Figure 4 shows the thematic breakdown of positive experiences shared by visitors. “Historical Texture and Natural Beauties” stands out as the most frequently praised aspect, underscoring the village’s architectural charm and surrounding landscape as its core touristic appeal. When Figure 4 is examined, the highest value among the subcategories is "Historical Texture and Natural Beauties" (65). This clearly demonstrates the impact of the village's unique architecture, stone streets, and the surrounding natural beauty on visitors. These elements indicate that the historical and natural heritage of Cumalıkızık are key factors that enhance the village's tourist appeal. Furthermore, the "Breakfast and Food Experience" (26) category reflects the significant contribution of the local gastronomic culture to visitor satisfaction. Visitors particularly emphasized the uniqueness of the village breakfast and regional flavours. Additionally, the "Hospitality and Local Culture" (20) category reveals that the warm attitude of the villagers and their authentic lifestyle are appreciated by visitors. The distribution of negative experiences of Cumalıkızık Village visitors between 2018-2024 by categories is in below.

Figure 5: Distribution of Negative Experiences of Cumalıkızık Village Visitors by Categories (2018-2024 by Categories)

Figure 5 shows the categorical distribution of the negative experiences of visitors in Cumalıkızık village. The most frequently cited issue, with 74 evaluations, is concentrated in the category of "Commercialization and the Attitude of the Local People." This indicates a perception that the village's authentic structure has been disrupted. Categories such as "Breakfast and Food Experience" (27), "Crowds and Noise" (17), and "Disappointment with the Historical Texture" (17) also reflect visitors' dissatisfaction. Particularly, "Parking and Transportation Issues" (13) draw attention to the infrastructure shortcomings in the village. This distribution reveals that both physical and social improvements are needed for Cumalıkızık to achieve its sustainable tourism goals. Overall, visitors emphasize the need for the preservation of the village's historical texture and the limitation of commercial activities. This highlights the need for a strong protection and regulation policy to maintain the village's UNESCO World Heritage status.

The village, in addition to being on the UNESCO World Heritage List, attracts thousands of visitors every year with its unique architecture, nature, and authentic atmosphere. This potential has led to the rapid development of the food and beverage sector in the region and intensified competition. Therefore, conducting a SWOT analysis for restaurants is of significant importance. To this end, a total of 1,617 Google reviews from the eight restaurants with the highest user ratings in the region for the year 2024 have been examined, and these reviews have been evaluated in terms of key factors such as customer satisfaction, complaints, and preferred features. Overall, the total number of reviews for these 8 restaurants has been recorded as 1,617, reflecting the customer interest in the restaurants in the region. The data provides an important foundation for understanding the competitive environment of a new restaurant opening in Cumalıkızık and determining its strategic positioning.

Table 2: Distribution of Visitor Experiences in Cumalıkızık Village by Year (2018–2024)

Code System	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	SUM
Positive Comments									
Food and Beverage	107	43	41	12	5	18	59	78	363
Service Quality	78	29	47	7	1	14	43	57	276
Atmosphere	41	33	31	6	10	13	50	71	255
Price/Value	17	16	12	3	2	1	21	5	77
Overall Satisfaction	41	9	16	3	1	7	28	34	139
Negative Comments									
Food and Beverage	101	34	5	5	17	1	16	6	185
Service Quality	63	47	5	6	11	7	7	5	144
Atmosphere	2	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	4
Price/Value	52	3	0	1	3	0	1	2	60
Overall Dissatisfaction	62	14	1	1	1	0	1	2	90
Others	8	0	0	2	7	2	7	3	24

Table 2 presents a detailed breakdown of customer reviews for restaurants in Cumalıkızık throughout 2024, categorized into positive and negative comments. The reviews are classified under subheadings such as "Food and Beverage," "Service Quality," "Atmosphere," "Price/Value," "Overall Satisfaction," and "Overall Dissatisfaction." A total of 1,617 reviews were examined, and evaluations were made for each restaurant based on these subcategories. In terms of positive reviews, the categories that received the most praise were Food and Beverage and Service Quality. Specifically, R1 stands out as the most notable restaurant with 107 positives "Food and Beverage" reviews and 78 positives "Service Quality" reviews. Similarly, R8 performed well in the positive "Food and Beverage" category with 78 reviews. In the Atmosphere category, R8 also stands out with 71 positive reviews. In the negative reviews category, the most frequently complained about topics were "Food and Beverage" and

“Price/Value.” Specifically, R1 draws attention as the restaurant with the highest number of complaints, receiving 101 negatives “Food and Beverage” reviews and 52 negatives “Price/Value” reviews. R2, on the other hand, highlighted issues in “Service Quality” with 47 negative reviews. Overall, positive reviews outnumber negative ones; however, negative comments in the “Price/Value” and “Service Quality” categories reveal areas that need improvement in the region’s restaurants. This table provides a crucial guide for a new restaurant to understand customer expectations, perform well in the highlighted areas, and make a difference by focusing on the frequently complained-about issues.

Following this situational analysis, the village was re-experienced in the form of a secret shopper, and similar findings were obtained. After analysing the current state of the village and the restaurants, a SWOT analysis was conducted with the participation of the municipal authorities. Ideas were generated during the process of developing an innovative business model and presented to the municipality. A value proposition canvas was created to assess the feasibility of the selected ideas, and the following proposals were developed to preserve the historical texture and natural beauty of Cumalıkızık village, enhance visitor satisfaction, sustainably improve the benefits of tourism for the local population, and strengthen the village’s UNESCO World Heritage status:

- Regular maintenance and restoration works can be conducted for historical buildings in the village, and national and international funds can be used to support these efforts.
- Information boards, mobile applications, and guided tours can be prepared for visitors.
- Training programs can be organized for the local community and businesses on the importance of preserving the historical texture.
- A welcome centre that explains the historical and cultural features of the village can be built at the entrance.
- Festivals promoting the history and culture of the village (e.g., "Cumalıkızık History and Taste Days") can be organized.
- The quality standards of breakfast spots in the village can be monitored, and menus featuring local products can be promoted.
- Concepts such as “Organic and Traditional Cumalıkızık Breakfast” can be created.
- Traditional handicraft workshops and exhibitions can be organized to increase interaction between visitors and local culture.
- Commercial activities in the village can be organized in specific areas without overshadowing the historical texture. For example, marketplaces can be established outside the village, and sales can be conducted there.
- The local community can be encouraged to offer only authentic and local products. The marketing of products unique to Cumalıkızık, instead of imitation or standardized items, can be promoted.
- Local merchants can be trained on visitor communication and commercial ethics.
- Vendors' aggressive behaviours can be regularly monitored.
- Parking can be moved to larger areas outside the village, transforming the village into a pedestrian-only zone. Transportation to the village centre can be provided by minibuses or electric vehicles.
- Village roads can be arranged for individuals with disabilities, with the installation of ramps and elevators.
- A system of online reservations and timed entry can be implemented to prevent overcrowding on days with high visitor numbers.

- Seasonal activities such as nature walks in the spring and photography events in the fall can be planned.
- Workshops or short-term learning programs about the historical texture and village life can be organized.
- Walking trails and bicycle paths within and around the village can be created, allowing visitors to experience the village's natural beauty.
- Quality standards can be established for restaurants and businesses in the village, and businesses that meet these standards can be awarded certifications.
- Regular inspections can be conducted by local authorities regarding commercialization and service quality. Quick solutions can be provided for complaints.
- Tourism intensity can be managed in a way that does not harm the environment or the village's residents. Visitor numbers can be balanced with sustainable tourism principles.
- The protection of green spaces, picnic areas, and walking paths around the village; and the adoption of ecological approaches to prevent damage to the natural texture are recommended.

Additionally, the following suggestions have been made for the restaurants:

- Packages such as “2-person breakfast + free beverage” or “4-person group discount” can be offered.
- Promotions like “Early Breakfast Discount” can be organized for guests arriving early in the morning.
- Special discounts for regular customers or benefits like a free breakfast after several visits can be provided.
- Special campaigns, contests, or “Like and Share” events can be organized on social media platforms (such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok).
- The restaurant menu can be made available for online orders to reach both local and out-of-town customers.
- Special menus can be prepared for days such as Mother's Day, Valentine's Day, or New Year's Eve.
- Suitable spaces can be provided for small celebrations, birthday events, or corporate meetings within the restaurant.
- Events like jam-making or bread-baking workshops can be organized to attract customers' attention.
- Partnerships can be made with hotels, boutique shops, or tour operators operating in the region.
- Group breakfasts can be organized for school trips, tour groups, and similar organizations.
- A corner selling local products can be created within the restaurant to both increase sales and enrich the visitor experience.
- A rotating menu with seasonal products can be created to offer new experiences for customers on every visit.
- “Tasting Days” can be organized where new products are offered for free or at a low cost.
- Visual appeal can be prioritized in presentations, preparing dishes that are shareable on social media.
- Aesthetic areas where visitors can take photos and share them can be created.
- Garden arrangements can offer a dining experience immersed in nature.

The proposed business models encourage women's active participation through initiatives such as traditional breakfast services, artisanal product stands, and craft workshops, potentially increasing female entrepreneurship and economic agency within the village. By organizing seasonal events such as walking tours and photography workshops, the models aim to generate flexible employment opportunities for local youth, particularly during tourism peaks in spring and autumn. The promotion of local products through in-restaurant sales corners and the development of certified quality standards are expected to boost household incomes by increasing the perceived and actual value of locally produced goods. Through stakeholder training programs and participatory development of business proposals, the models foster a sense of community ownership and improve local capacities for collective action

5. Conclusion

This study has examined the role of emerging business models for cultural tourism by considering Cumalıkızık village, a UNESCO World Heritage Village, as a case study. By conducting word frequency analysis in MAXQDA of 2,135 Tripadvisor and 1,617 Google reviews, this study has come up with significant strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the regional cultural tourism industry. The findings suggest the necessity of the application of sustainable tourism policies that promote heritage conservation along with economic development. The research indicates that while Cumalıkızık's historic texture (65%), natural landscapes (26%), and locals' hospitality (20%) are most frequently referred to in a positive way, there are some issues too. Commercialization (74 negative mentions), overcrowding (17 mentions), and inadequate infrastructure (13 mentions) are all significant threats to the village's authenticity and tourists' satisfaction. In addition, restaurant companies in the country are confronted with both opportunities and operational issues, including food quality (363 positive vs. 185 negative postings), service standards (276 positive vs. 144 negative postings), and pricing strategies (77 positive vs. 60 negative postings).

This study presents new business models to address these challenges. These models will enhance the visitor experience and promote sustainable economic growth. Recommendations include integrating digital visitor engagement, data-driven tourism infrastructure planning, controlled commercialisation strategy, and capacity-development programs for local stakeholders. Restaurant activities must be reorganised through strategic pricing, experiential dining concepts, and digital campaign programs to improve Cumalıkızık's tourism landscape. This research emphasises the importance of stakeholder-driven, data-based cultural tourism strategy. Cumalıkızık can become a more prominent sustainable cultural tourist destination while retaining its unique social and historic essence by integrating creative business models. Developed business models will contribute to local entrepreneurship, especially among women, increase household income through direct sales of local goods, and promote seasonal employment aligned with tourism flows. The implementation of these innovative business models will lead to tangible benefits for the local population. These outcomes align with broader sustainable development objectives and ensure the preservation of the village's cultural and social fabric. The Bursa Metropolitan Municipality is well-positioned to lead infrastructure-related implementations, while local NGOs and cooperatives can champion community-based tourism and training activities. Strategic coordination among these actors will be vital for sustaining impact. Specifically, the models promote female entrepreneurship, provide seasonal employment opportunities for local youth, increase the value and marketability of local products, and enhance community involvement in sustainable tourism planning. These outcomes align with broader sustainable development objectives and ensure the preservation of the village's cultural and social fabric. While these models are not radically

innovative on a global scale, their contextual adaptation to Cumalıkızık's unique socio-cultural environment makes them significantly impactful at the local level. So, the Bursa Metropolitan Municipality can lead the implementation of mobility solutions (e.g., electric shuttles) easily, while local cooperatives may coordinate 'traditional product certification' systems.

While the proposed models may not be globally revolutionary, their contextual relevance and co-creative development process with local actors make them uniquely adapted to Cumalıkızık's socio-cultural ecosystem. This context-driven innovation offers a replicable framework for other small heritage destinations seeking to balance tourism growth with cultural preservation. Other future research studies may extend upon the work through long-term evaluations of such innovations as well as tests for transferring applicability into other cultural heritage travel destinations. In addition, more advanced quantitative techniques, such as predictive modelling or sentiment analysis, can potentially enhance visitor experience and business performance measurement in the future.

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